

Improved air Processability of Organic Photovoltaics by Using a Stabilizing Antioxidant to Prevent Thermal oxidation

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Abstract

During the production of organic solar cells, the exposure of constituting materials and resulting devices to light, heat, oxygen and water is a potential source of degradation. We show that thermo-oxidation of the active materials occurs upon annealing the active layer or upon stirring the active materials solutions in air at elevated temperatures. By comparing various blends of donor polymers with fullerene or non-fullerene acceptors, the fullerene is identified to be the most susceptible component to thermal oxidation in both film and solution, while the polymer remains unaffected. In both cases, the effect on the photovoltaic device performance consists predominantly in a decreased short-circuit current (J_{SC}), suggesting that the underlying degradation mechanism is the same in the solid state and in solution. In addition, we find that thermo-oxidation of the active layer during annealing of the device can be decelerated by blending nickel(II) dibutyldithiocarbamate ($Ni(dtc)_2$) as antioxidant additive into the active layer. While small concentrations of additive stabilize the J_{SC} and therefore the power conversion efficiency, higher contents negatively affect device performance. On the other hand, thermo-oxidation of the active materials in solution during stirring in air at elevated temperatures can be avoided for several hours by adding as little as 0.5% of $Ni(dtc)_2$. The observation that the antioxidant is consumed during stabilization of the active materials suggests a sacrificial protection mechanism.

Keywords

Thermal oxidation, Organic solar cells, Stabilization, Metal halide Complex, $Ni(dtc)_2$, temperature stability

1 Introduction

A viable method for converting solar radiation into electrical power is the use of organic photovoltaic (OPV) cells. OPV modules although still somewhat inferior to inorganic technologies in terms of efficiency ¹, exhibit different unique properties, such as flexibility, light weight, semitransparency, and availability in different colors ²⁻⁸, which make them ideally suited for integration into buildings, mobile applications and textiles. As a major advantage over traditional PV technologies, they can be manufactured from solution by roll-to-roll (R2R) coating methods ⁹, which allows cost-effective mass production with high throughputs.

A serious drawback of OPV is that it shows severe degradation upon exposure to light, heat, oxygen, and water ¹⁰⁻²⁵.

While the effects of light and humidity can be minimized with relatively little effort, oxygen and heat can hardly be avoided in a cost-effective industrial R2R production. In order to keep investment and operating costs low, the whole manufacturing process has to be performed under ambient atmosphere. Moreover, the production of OPV modules from solution usually involves drying and annealing steps at elevated temperatures of up to 140 °C in order to eliminate residual solvents, establish a favorable active layer morphology or to activate cross-linking agents, which make a coated layer more robust and, by this, prevent its re-dissolution upon coating the next overlying layer of the OPV multilayer stack (e.g., to coat water-based silver nanowires on top of cross-linked PEDOT:PSS). Thus, even when processing in the dark at controlled humidity, the combination of heat and oxygen can lead to thermal oxidation of the organic materials ^{21,23}. Defects in polymers ²⁶ are formed by reaction with oxygen in radical reactions^{10,19,227-31}.

Fullerenes are also known to be oxidized but also act as radical scavengers, thereby protecting polymers³²⁻³⁴. Oxygenation of polymers and fullerenes leads to reduced charge carrier mobility, which in turn reduces the performance of the OPV device, affecting mainly the short circuit current (J_{sc}), leading to decreased power conversion efficiencies (PCE). This issue needs to be solved in order to be able to produce highly efficient organic solar cells in ambient air²³.

One step on the route to solve these issues is to prevent degradation of the active materials inside the solution by using stabilizing additives¹³³⁵⁻³⁷. We have previously shown that the organometallic chelate complex nickel(II) dibutyldithiocarbamate ($Ni(dtc)_2$) can act as an antioxidant in organic solar cells upon illumination in air by stabilizing the active materials against photo-oxidation³⁸. This cheap antioxidating additive is known as stabilizing additive for organic substances since 1970³⁷. It acts as scavenger that traps radicals like HO- and PO-radicals³⁶. On top it is reported that the metal complex can act as well as singlet oxygen quencher^{35,36,39,40} and antiozonant^{37,39}. As a consequence, this work focuses on the effect of air-processed OPV on PCE and the stabilization effect of the additive $Ni(dtc)_2$.

The two main investigated systems were the fullerene acceptor phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) in combination with either the commercial donor polymer PV2000 or poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl) (P3HT), as these material systems show good trade-off between efficiency, price and stability and are thus relevant for production of OPV in ambient atmosphere. In this paper, we examine the thermal oxidation behavior of these systems and the effect on the respective solar cells performance, when active layers are annealed in air or the active materials solutions are stirred in air at elevated temperatures. Moreover, $Ni(dtc)_2$ is investigated as an antioxidating additive to prevent this degradation by adding it to the active materials solution.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample preparation

Solar cells with different active layer material combinations were prepared. As donors, the polymers **PV2000** by Raynergy Tek and poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl) (**P3HT**) were utilized. As acceptors, the fullerenes phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (**PC₆₀BM**), bis(1-[3-(methoxycarbonyl)propyl]-1-phenyl)-[6,6]C₆₂ (**bisPC₆₀BM**), and 1',1'',4',4''-Tetrahydro-di[1,4]methanonaphthaleno [1,2:2',3',56,60:2'',3''][5,6]fullerene-C₆₀ (**ICBA**) as well as the non-fullerene acceptors (NFA) 2,2'-[[6,6,12,12-Tetrakis(4-hexylphenyl)-6,12-dihydrodithieno[2,3-d:2',3'-d']-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']dithiophene-2,8-diyl]bis[methyldiylidene(3-oxo-1H-indene-2,1(3H)-diylidene)]]bis[propanedinitrile] (**ITIC**) and (5Z,5'Z)-5,5'-{(4,9-dihydro-4,4,9,9-tetraoctyl-s-indaceno[1,2-b:5,6-b']-dithiophene-2,7-diyl) bis[2,1,3-benzothiadiazole-7,4-diyl(Z)methylylidene]]bis(3-ethyl-2-thioxo-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one) (**O-IDTBR**). For all different combinations, the same inverted solar cell stack was prepared as follows: 25 mm x 25 mm pre-structured ITO glass substrates from VisionTek were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with acetone and isopropanol for 5 min each. As electron transport layer (ETL), a solution of zinc oxide nanoparticles (N10 from Avantama) was doctor bladed onto the samples and annealed at 120 °C for 4 min at ambient atmosphere. The active layer solutions were prepared and stirred overnight in nitrogen atmosphere and doctor bladed in air onto the ETL. Subsequently, PEDOT:PSS (HTL Solar from Heraeus) was doctor bladed in air as hole transport layer (HTL). After that, the cells were annealed for 4 min at 140 °C in nitrogen atmosphere. Finally, a layer of silver nanowires (ClearOhm from Cambrios) was doctor bladed in air as top electrode. The cells were laser structured to obtain six individual solar cells with 0.1 cm² active area per substrate. Finally, all devices were annealed at 120 °C in nitrogen atmosphere.

2.2 IV-measurements

The current-voltage characteristics measurements were performed in nitrogen atmosphere with a Keysight B2901A source measurement unit under illumination with a class AAA solar simulator from LOT Quantum Design providing 1000 W/m².

2.3 Thermal stability measurements

The thermal stability of the active layer materials in the presence of air was investigated at different stages of the sample preparation. Firstly, after deposition of the active layers, they were annealed at elevated temperatures (100-140 °C) on a hotplate in ambient atmosphere. Each active layer contained certain amounts of Ni(dtc)₂ in order to check the influence of the additive on thermal stability. A box covering the samples ensured that this was performed in the dark. These annealing steps were performed after the deposition of the PEDOT:PSS layer or after finalizing the overall cell. Further, solutions of the active layer materials were exposed to air and stirred at 120 °C before coating onto the substrate. Devices were fabricated from these solutions after certain stirring times and were measured after finalization of the solar cell. These solutions were produced with certain amounts of Ni(dtc)₂.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Thermal oxidation of solar cells

Annealing steps are indispensable in the production of organic solar cells as they serve the evaporation of residual solvents, the cross-linking of the HTL and for most active material systems the optimization of the active layer morphology^{41,42}. In order to quantify the detrimental

effect of annealing in air on the four active layer systems PV2000:PCBM, PV2000:ITIC, P3HT:PCBM, and P3HT:O-IDTBR, the corresponding devices were prepared under two different conditions: after the deposition of the PEDOT:PSS layer, one set of devices was annealed at 140 °C in air, Figure 1 shows the resulting performances for the four different active layer combinations, where the full boxes represent cells annealed in nitrogen and the open boxes represent devices that have been annealed in air. Three of the four systems (PV2000:PCBM, P3HT:PCBM, P3HT:IDTBR) show a reduced PCE upon annealing in air, which is caused by a reduced short-circuit current (J_{SC}), while open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and fill factor (FF) remain almost unaffected. Quantitatively, the relative decrease of PCE is 20% (5.9% vs. 4.7%) for PV2000:PCBM, 25% (2.7% vs. 2.0%) for P3HT:PCBM, and 10% (6.2% vs. 5.6%) for P3HT:IDTBR. Only the system PV2000:ITIC shows the same performance for both annealing conditions.

As, apart from the active materials, the layer stacks are identical for all four systems and one of these systems is found to withstand 4 min of annealing in air without any loss in performance, it seems reasonable to conclude that it is the active layer which is most affected by annealing in air, while the charge extraction layers used in this investigation remain stable under these conditions. Although it is known from literature that the interfacial layers, namely ETL and HTL, can contribute to the degradation of the active layer and/or the whole device⁴³, our results suggest that under these conditions thermo-oxidation of the active materials dominates the overall device degradation. This is further supported by the finding that the same degree of degradation is observed when annealing the cells in air right after the AL coating, i.e., before the HTL is coated on top, which corroborates that the degradation is not related to the AL/HTL interface (see

Figure S1). It is to note that a preferential degradation originating from the interface towards the ETL (ZnO) cannot be excluded at this point.

We assign the observed degradation behavior to thermo-oxidation of at least one of the components of the active layer. As shown previously in the case of photo-oxidation of the active layer⁴⁴ this leads to the increase of mobile majority carriers and subsequently to the screening of the built-in field of the device, which in turn causes the observed reduction in J_{sc} .

Figure 1. Effect of annealing on the performance of OPV cells with different active layer systems. Each system has been annealed at 140 °C for 4 min after deposition of the PEDOT:PSS layer, either in nitrogen (filled boxes) or in air (open boxes).

3.2 Thermal oxidation of the active materials in solution

In order to find out which components of the active layers are affected by annealing in air, the components are exposed to air while still in solution. This represents the situation in an industrial production, in which the active material solutions (based on non-halogenated solvents) are heated both prior as well as during the coating process (in air) for several hours to ensure a complete dissolution and a particle-free coating. For this purpose, PV2000:PCBM solutions are prepared in four different ways. Solutions 1 and 2 are prepared by dissolving PV2000 and PCBM in o-xylene simultaneously (under nitrogen) and subsequently stirring the resulting solutions in nitrogen or air, respectively, at 120 °C for 24 h. Stirring in air was performed by opening the vial lid for a short period of time in air in order to get gas exchange between the vial and the surrounding environment and closing it again before stirring the solution further. For preparing solutions 3 and 4, one of the components (PV2000 or PCBM, respectively) is dissolved in o-xylene and stirred overnight in nitrogen atmosphere at 120 °C. Subsequently, the solution is exposed ambient atmosphere and stirred at 120 °C for additional 24 h. Finally, the other component (PCBM or PV2000, respectively) is added in nitrogen atmosphere and further stirred at 120 °C for few hours until its complete dissolution in order to decrease the impact of further thermo-oxidation.

The PCE values of the devices prepared from these solutions are shown in Figure 2 (top). Stirring a PCBM + PV2000 solution (solution 2) for 24h at 120°C in air causes a reduced PCE of

5.4% compared to 7.0% for the reference (solution 1) stirred in nitrogen. The current density-voltage (JV) curves (Figure 2, bottom) show that the efficiency drop is mainly due to a drop in J_{SC} drops, while fill factor and open-circuit voltage remain mainly unaffected, in accordance with the behavior of the devices treated in air after the deposition of the HTL (Figure 1). Almost the same J_{SC} loss is observed for solution 4 (PV2000 stirred under nitrogen, PCBM stirred in air), whereas solution 3 (PV2000 stirred in air, PCBM stirred in nitrogen) provides the same performance as solution 1 (both components stirred in N_2). In all cases, FF and V_{oc} remain almost unaffected. In addition, it is to note that no performance loss is observed, if the PCBM solution is stirred in air at room temperature (see Figure S2).

Figure 2. Top: PCE boxplot of solar cells prepared from solutions of PV2000 and PCBM stirred at 120 °C under different atmospheres (variation 1 (black): PCBM + PV2000 stirred in nitrogen, variation 2 (red): PV2000 + PCBM stirred in air for 24h, variation 3 (green): PV2000 stirred 24h

in air, variation 4 (blue): PCBM stirred 24h in air). Bottom: corresponding jV curves of these cells.

These results suggest that PV2000 is stable in the presence of oxygen at the temperatures required for annealing. This is in line with the results obtained on full devices (see Figure 1), which show that the performance of the system PV2000:ITIC does not degrade upon annealing in air. This leads us to the conclusion that it is mainly the fullerene component which is thermo-oxidized in the presence of oxygen at elevated temperatures, both in solution and films, and thus leads to the reduced performance of the resulting devices.

3.3 Thermo-oxidation of different fullerene derivatives

In previous works, the susceptibility of P3HT:fullerene-based active layers to photo-oxidation has been shown to depend on the fullerene LUMO level and/or its number of substituents^{24,45-47}. Especially the high-LUMO fullerene derivatives bisPCBM (-3.60 eV)²⁴ and ICBA (-3.53 eV)²⁴ were found to be sensitive to illumination in air. In order to investigate their stability under thermo-oxidative conditions, a series of organic solar cells with active layers of P3HT:PCBM, P3HT:bisPCBM and P3HT:ICBA were prepared after stirring the active layer solutions at 120 °C in ambient atmosphere for different times.

Figure 3 shows that for all three active layer systems, the device performance decreases with increasing stirring time in the presence of oxygen. Furthermore, the devices containing bisPCBM and ICBA exhibit increased degradation compared to PCBM. After stirring the active materials for 25 hours in air, the PCBM based cells still have >60% of the PCE of a device prepared from undegraded solution (i.e., no stirring in air), whereas the bisPCBM and ICBA based cells maintained only ~40% and ~20% of their initial values, respectively. Obviously, in analogy to

photo-oxidation, the additional substitution to the C_{60} cage in the fullerenes bisPCBM and ICBA also increases their susceptibility towards thermo-oxidation. This result confirms once more that the fullerene is the most sensitive component to degradation under these conditions.

Figure 3. PCE of organic solar cells of the structure glass/ITO/ZnO/P3HT:fullerene/PEDOT:PSS/Ag NW (fullerene = PC60BM, bisPCBM, ICBA); prepared from active layer solutions (P3HT and fullerene in *o*-xylene) which have been stirred at 120 °C in air for different times before deposition.

3.4 Stabilization by means of an antioxidant

Several antioxidants have been used successfully as additives for the protection of organic solar cells^{35–38}. One of the promising candidates is the organometallic complex $Ni(dtc)_2$, which has been shown to reduce photo-oxidation of P3HT:fullerene cells^{38,48,49}. In order to test whether $Ni(dtc)_2$ also works as an additive against thermo-oxidation, solar cells with PV2000:PCBM as active layer were produced with different amounts of $Ni(dtc)_2$, namely 0.5wt%, 1.0wt%, 2.0wt%, and 5.0wt% with respect to the polymer PV2000. The initial performance of these cells is listed in Table 1. While the overall performance is slightly increased by the addition of 0.5wt% $Ni(dtc)_2$, it is strongly reduced for higher amounts of the additive, especially due to losses in V_{oc}

and FF, thus indicating an extraction barrier. Furthermore, the JV curves (see Figure S3) show pronounced S-shapes for Ni amounts of more than 0.5 wt%, indicating a strong charge injection barrier caused by the Ni complex. One possible explanation for this behavior could be the accumulation of the additive at an interface (e.g. on the surface of the active layer), while the drop in V_{OC} may stem from an additional energy level introduced by $Ni(dtc)_2$.

Subsequently, the cells were degraded on a hot plate at 100 °C in ambient atmosphere in the dark and measured after different times of degradation. It is to note that neither visible changes in the device nor significant spectral changes in the active material absorption (see Figure S6) are observed under these annealing conditions. The resulting plots of PCE and J_{SC} vs. degradation time are shown in Figure 4. They show significant degradation of PCE for all samples, mainly due to loss in J_{SC} , but also in V_{OC} and FF (see Figure S4). This behavior is in close analogy to the results displayed in Figure 1 and is therefore ascribed to photo-oxidation of PCBM. After 6 h of annealing in air, all variations loose at least 30% of their initial PCE and 15% of their initial J_{SC} . However, with increasing concentration of $Ni(dtc)_2$, cell degradation slows down (Figure 4). After 1 h of degradation, the sample with 5% $Ni(dtc)_2$ still shows the initial J_{SC} value, followed by the device with 2% $Ni(dtc)_2$ that still maintains 90% of the initial value, whereas the device without $Ni(dtc)_2$ has lost 25% of its initial J_{SC} . Thus, after 30 min, the absolute J_{SC} value of the device with 5wt% $Ni(dtc)_2$ exceeds those of all other samples, despite its initially lower value. While in this case the FF decreases similarly to all other samples, V_{oc} stays constant (see Figure S5).

Figure 4. Performances of OPV cells with different amounts of $\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})_2$ (in weight percent of PV2000) after different times of annealing at 100 °C in air. Top graphs show normalized and bottom graphs absolute values.

Table 1. Initial performance values of PV2000:PCBM OPV cells with different amounts of $\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})_2$

$\text{Ni}(\text{dtc})_2$ amount	PCE	FF	J_{sc}	V_{oc}
0%	4.9%	59%	11.0 mA/cm ²	0.77 V
0.5%	5.2%	59%	11.6 mA/cm ²	0.76 V
1%	3.6%	53%	9.8 mA/cm ²	0.71 V
2%	2.9%	50%	9.3 mA/cm ²	0.63 V
5%	2.2%	48%	9.9 mA/cm ²	0.46 V

These observations demonstrate that the addition of Ni(dtc)₂ to PV2000:PCBM solar cells serves to reduce the rate of thermo-oxidation during annealing. Unfortunately, during the whole course of degradation displayed in Figure 4, the stabilizing effect by Ni(dtc)₂ is never able to compensate the initial performance limitations in terms of absolute PCE, due to the losses in V_{oc} and FF caused by the addition of Ni(dtc)₂. For the active layer system under investigation, the Ni complex is thus not appropriate for protecting the corresponding devices during annealing.

In order to test the stabilization capability of the nickel complex in solution, experiments with P3HT:PCBM and PV2000:PCBM organic solar cells were performed, where the solutions of the active materials (either with or without 0.5wt% Ni(dtc)₂ of the polymer weight) were stirred at 120 °C in air for different time periods before deposition on the glass substrate. The devices were subsequently finished in nitrogen atmosphere. Figure 5 shows the performance of P3HT:PCBM and PV2000:PCBM devices as a function of exposure time of the solutions with and without 0.5% nickel complex to air. For P3HT:PCBM based devices, the initial performance of devices with and without Ni(dtc)₂ is identical, which is in accordance with previous studies³⁸, whereas the initial PCE values of PV2000:PCBM based devices are reduced by 1.5% (absolute) when prepared from the solution containing the Ni complex. More importantly however, both active materials systems experience a clear stabilizing effect against thermo-oxidation by the addition of Ni(dtc)₂ to the solutions. The PCE and J_{sc} values remain constant for up to 10 h for both material systems when 0.5% Ni(dtc)₂ has been added to the solutions, whereas for the solutions without additive significant degradation is observed, analogously to the situation shown in Figure 2. Obviously, addition of as little as 0.5% Ni(dtc)₂ (in wt% of the polymer weight) to the solutions of active layer materials is sufficient to stabilize them against thermo-oxidation during stirring overnight in air.

After about 10 h of stirring the active layer solutions in air, the performance of the cells prepared from these solutions starts to decrease significantly for both material systems (Figure 5). As the antioxidant effect of Ni(dtc)₂ has been shown by UV/Vis spectroscopy to be at least partially sacrificial³⁸, the increase in the degradation rate is probably due to the fact that the Ni complex has been fully consumed at this point in time. Unfortunately, due to the low concentration of the Ni complex in the films and the spectral overlap of its absorption spectrum with those of the active layer components, the quantification of this depletion effect by UV/Vis spectroscopy is not possible in this case³⁸. However, another observation supports this interpretation. The PV2000:PCBM:Ni(dtc)₂ samples, which exhibit lower initial values of FF and V_{oc}, due to the detrimental effect of the additive, show a gradual increase of both parameters with ongoing solution ageing (indicated by the first red arrow). FF and V_{oc} reach their maximum values which are observed in cells without the Ni complex after about 10 h (Figure 5), which is also the point in time when the degradation rate of the J_{SC} values accelerates. Both effects are in agreement with the gradual depletion of Ni(dtc)₂ during the exposure of the solutions to air, which leads to the complete consumption of the Ni complex after about 10 hours of stirring in air.

Figure 5. Performance parameters of OPV cells of two different active layer systems (left: P3HT:PCBM, right: PV2000:PCBM) prepared from solutions of active layer materials, with and without 0.5% Ni(dtc)₂, after stirring in air at 120 °C for different times.

4 Conclusion

Degradation of different solar cells due to annealing of the device or stirring the active layer solution in air at elevated temperatures was reported. The degradation mainly effects the J_{SC} that is reduced significantly. Thermo-oxidation is identified as root cause for active layer degradation of P3HT:PCBM and PV2000:PCBM based solar cells. In both blends, the fullerene has been identified as the component that is degraded during thermal oxidation in both film and solution, while the polymer remains unaffected. In contrast, the fullerene-free system PV2000:ITIC shows no degradation in ambient atmosphere at elevated temperatures in the dark. Our results suggest that the underlying degradation mechanism is the same in the solid state and in solution, since in both cases the same materials as well as the same device parameters are affected upon degradation. Thermal oxidation of the active layer during annealing of the device can be suppressed by blending the metal-organic complex $Ni(dtc)_2$ into the active layer, which stabilizes the J_{SC} and consequently the PCE. As the complex is consumed in the sacrificial protection mechanism, degradation can only be delayed but not prevented, which depends on the amount of complex added. Additive concentration is limited to an upper maximum concentration, above which device performance is affected negatively, as indicated by the formation of S-shapes in the JV curves. The greatest benefit of $Ni(dtc)_2$ lies in the stabilization of solutions of active materials during stirring in air at elevated temperatures, where thermal oxidation can be avoided for several hours by adding as little as 0.5% of the Ni complex.

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